

Synthesis and Biological Activity of Some New N⁵-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl thioacetyl-N^{1'}-benzylidene Hydrazines

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The synthesis and antibacterial activity of twenty new N-benzylidene derivatives of 5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl-thioacetyl hydrazines have been described. The title compounds were synthesised by the condensation of 5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl-thioacetyl hydrazines with different aromatic aldehydes.

In recent years 1,3,4-thiadiazole nucleus and its derivatives have received much attention as potential bactericides¹, fungicides², insecticides³, herbicides^{4,5} and flower control agents⁶. Various hydrazine derivatives have been associated with anthelmintic and antifungal⁷ activity. A number of substituted N-benzylidene derivatives also have been reported to possess bactericidal⁸, acaricidal⁹, fungicidal¹⁰ and herbicidal¹¹ activities. With these findings in view it was proposed to synthesise some new N-benzylidene derivatives of 5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl-thioacetyl hydrazines according to the Scheme I given below :

Scheme—1

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The synthesised compounds were characterised by ir spectroscopy,

thin layer chromatography and elemental analyses of C, H and N. Tlc was performed on silica gel layers and spots were visualized by exposing the developed and dry plates to I_2 vapours. The ir spectra showed characteristic absorption bands around 3400 cm^{-1} (NH), 1680 cm^{-1} (C=O) and 1600 cm^{-1} (C=N).

The key intermediate 2-mercapto-5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles^{1,2} were obtained by the cyclisation of N⁴-arylthiosemicarbazides^{1,2}.

2-(5-Arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl-thio)ethylacetate (I): A solution of 2-mercapto-5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazole (0.01 mole) and NaOH (0.01 mole) in 30 ml ethanol was heated under reflux for about 30 minutes. To this was added ethyl bromoacetate (0.0 mole) and the resulting mixture refluxed for about 4 hrs. After cooling the solution was poured on ice and the solid mass thus separated was crystallised from ethanol.

2-Mercaptoacetyl-5-arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl hydrazide^{1,4}(II): The solution of I (0.01 mole) in ethanol was reacted with 99% hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mole) by heating it under reflux for about 2 hrs, in absolute ethanol. The solid mass which separated out, was concentrated and filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

N⁵-Arylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl-thioacetyl-N^{1'}-benzylidene hydrazines(III): To a solution of II (0.01 mole) in 25 ml ethanol was added ethanolic solution of appropriate aldehyde (0.01 mole) and the resulting mixture was refluxed for about 5 hrs. The solid mass which separated on cooling was filtered and finally recrystallised from ethanol.

Biological screening: All the new synthesised compounds were screened for their antibacterial and insecticidal activities. Antibacterial activity was determined using agar plate diffusion method^{1,5} against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Escherichia coli*.

Similarly the insecticidal activity was carried out on adult male and female cockroaches (*Periplaneta americana*) by surface application method.

Results and Discussion

The results of antibacterial activity indicated that most of the compounds exhibited effective activity

TABLE-1

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula
1.	H	2-OCH ₃	216	75	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂
2.	H	3-NO ₂	242	55	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₃ S ₂
3.	H	4-NO ₂	239	50	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₃ S ₂
4.	H	3-OH	210	84	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂
5.	H	4-OH	224	90	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂
6.	H	4-Cl	234	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₃ Cl
7.	H	3,4(OCH ₃) ₂	181	78	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₅ S ₂
8.	4-Cl	2-OCH ₃	210	72	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂ Cl
9.	4-Cl	4-NO ₂	222	52	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₆ O ₃ S ₂ Cl
10.	4-Cl	3-NO ₂	203	48	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₆ O ₃ S ₂ Cl
11.	4-Cl	3-OH	192	68	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂ Cl
12.	4-Cl	4-OH	230	63	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂ Cl
13.	4-Cl	4-Cl	233	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂ Cl ₂
14.	4-Cl	3,4(OCH ₃) ₂	228	74	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₅ S ₂ Cl
15.	4-OH	2-OCH ₃	220	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₅ S ₂
16.	4-OH	3-NO ₂	198	56	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₅ S ₂
17.	4-OH	4-NO ₂	201	50	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₅ S ₂
18.	4-CH ₃	3-OH	209	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂
19.	4-CH ₃	4-OH	215	72	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂
20.	4-CH ₃	4-Cl	219	76	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₃ S ₂ Cl

All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis.

TABLE 2—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY

Mean area inhibition after 24 hours

Sl. No.	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
1.	++	-	++
2.	++	++	-
3.	+++	+++	+
4.	++	-	+
5.	++	-	+
6.	+++	++	-
7.	++	++	-
8.	++	++	-
9.	+	++	-
10.	+++	+	-
11.	+++	++	+
12.	++	+++	++
13.	++	+	++
14.	++	+	++
15.	++	-	-
16.	++	+	-
17.	+++	++	-
18.	++	-	-
19.	++	+	-
20.	+	+	+

- = No inhibition.
 + = Zone size 6-8 mm.
 ++ = Zone size 8-12 mm.
 +++ = Zone size greater than 12 mm.

against *S. aureus* and moderate against *S. typhi* and *E. coli*.

Of all the compounds those containing nitro and chloro groups at para position, as well as nitro at meta position, exhibited activity of higher order.

Insecticidal activity of all the compounds were found to be moderate at 0.5% concentration.

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References

- V. ETABLISSEMENT, FR. DEMANDE 2,356,656, 1978; *Chem. Abs.*, 1978, **89**, 163587y.
- L. NUSSLER, E. A. PIERROCH and K. RORDER, (Schering A. G.) U. S. Pat. 4,061,645; *Chem. Abs.*, 1978, **88**, 62397k.
- S. S. TIWARI, A. K. SENGUPTA and J. KUMAR, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1970, **32**, 91.
- C. METZGER, L. EUR, R. R. SCHMIDT, (Bayer A. G.) *Ger. Offen.*, 2,411,288, 1975; *Chem. Abs.*, 1975, **84**, 17367g.
- J. KRENZER, (Veliscol Chemical Corporation) U. S., 4,052,193; *Chem. Abs.*, 1978, **88**, 22929d.
- K. UEKI, Japan Kokai, 73,52,933; *Chem. Abs.*, 1973, **79**, 133667a.
- R. CAVIER and R. RIPS, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1965, **8**, 706.
- W. HOYLE and G. A. HOWARTH, *Brit. Pat.* 1,290,914; *Chem. Abs.*, 1973, **78**, 16018h.
- R. BORSCH, *Ger. Offen.*, 2,326,788; *Chem. Abs.*, 1974, **80**, 70518a.
- Takeda Chemical Industries Ltd., Japan, 9887; *Chem. Abs.*, 1964, **61**, 12007e.
- G. KANGARS, U. S. Pat., 3,745,215; *Chem. Abs.*, 1973, **79**, 78412m.
- J. KUMAR, Ph.D. Thesis, "Search for New Pesticides", Lucknow University, 1971.
- Y. YA KAZAKOV and I. YA POSTOVSKII, *Izvest. Vyshikh Ucheb. Zavedenii, Khim i khim Technol.*, 1961, **55**, 28415.
- A. K. SEN GUPTA and A. K. RAMRAKHYANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 742.
- R. S. VARMA and S. A. IMAM, *Indian J. Microbiol.* 1973, **13**, 45.